

Supplementary files of chapter 4 Peppermint oil and sweets in pediatric irritable bowel syndrome and functional abdominal pain: a randomized trial.

Supplementary figures

Supplementary figure 1. Sankey diagram of treatment switch at T2 per treatment group.

Supplementary figure 2. Mean abdominal pain intensity scores at T0 to T3.

Supplementary figure 3. Mean abdominal pain duration per day at T0 to T3.

Supplementary figure 4. Mean abdominal pain frequency in days per week at T0 to T3.

Supplementary tables

Supplementary table 1. Overview of endpoints

Endpoint	Instrument	T0 Baseline	T1 4 weeks after start treatment	T2 End of treatment	T3 4 weeks follow-up
Abdominal pain	Abdominal pain diaries	X	X	X	X
Defecation pattern	Abdominal pain diaries	X	X	X	X
School absence	Abdominal pain diaries	X	X	X	X
Use of pain medication	Abdominal pain diaries	X	X	X	X
Adequate relief	Binary question on adequate relief		X	X	X
Depression and anxiety	Revised Child Anxiety and Depression Scale-short version (RCADS-25) ³⁴	X		X	
Quality of life	Pediatric Quality of Life (PedsQL 4.0) ³⁵	X		X	
Impact of complaints	Self-designed questionnaire consisting of four 5-point Likert scales	X			
Expectancy of treatment	Self-designed question consisting of an 11-point Likert scale	X			
Ease of use and taste	Self-designed questionnaire consisting of two 5-point Likert scales			X	
Adverse events	Abdominal pain diaries and history taking by physician		X	X	X

Supplementary table 2. Participant' and parental reports on impact of complaints, level of concern, and preference and expected improvement of allocated treatment.

	Peppermint oil (N = 75) Participant N = 60 Parent 1 N = 64 Parent 2 N = 42	Placebo (N = 75) Participant N = 60 Parent 1 N = 69 Parent 2 N = 41	Peppermint sweets (N = 78) Participant N = 65 Parent 1 N = 71 Parent 2 N = 34	P-value
Impact on child's daily life activities, mean (SD) ¶				
Participant	2.3 (0.9)	2.3 (1.1)	2.3 (1.1)	
Parent 1	2.5 (1.0)	2.6 (1.2)	2.6 (1.1)	
Parent 2	2.2 (1.1)	2.4 (1.1)	2.6 (1.2)	
Impact on child's emotions, mean (SD) ¶				
Participant	2.2 (1.0)	2.4 (1.0)	2.2 (1.2)	
Parent 1	2.5 (0.9)	2.6 (1.0)	2.6 (1.0)	
Parent 2	2.4 (1.0)	2.5 (1.0)	2.6 (0.9)	
Level of concern about abdominal complaints, mean (SD) ¶				
Participant	2.2 (1.1)	1.9 (1.1)	1.9 (1.2)	
Parent 1	2.4 (1.0)	2.6 (1.1)	2.6 (1.0)	
Parent 2	2.3 (1.1)	2.5 (1.2)	2.4 (0.8)	
Subjective severity of complaints, mean (SD) †				
Participant	2.8 (0.8)	2.8 (0.9)	2.8 (0.9)	
Parent 1	2.6 (0.8)	2.9 (0.8)	2.8 (0.7)	
Parent 2	2.7 (0.8)	2.7 (0.8)	2.7 (0.8)	
Expected improvement due to study medication, mean (SD) ‡				
Participant	6.5 (2.1)	6.2 (2.1)	6.1 (2.4)	.53
Parent 1	5.5 (2.2)	5.2 (2.5)	5.6 (2.5)	.50
Parent 2	6.1 (1.4)	5.7 (1.6)	5.1 (2.3)	.09
Drug preference, n (%)				
– Mild preference for peppermint oil Participant	8 (13.3)	7 (11.7)	6 (9.2)	
– Strong preference for peppermint oil Participant	11 (18.3)	17 (28.3)	18 (27.7)	
– Mild preference for peppermint sweets Participant	5 (8.3)	3 (5.0)	7 (10.8)	
– Strong preference for peppermint sweets Participant	10 (16.7)	7 (11.7)	10 (15.4)	

¶ Impact on the child's daily life activities and emotions was measured with a 5-point Likert scale, with 0 indication no impact and 4 a great impact.

▯ Level of concern about abdominal complaints was measured with a 5-point Likert scale, with 0 indication no concern and 4 a great amount of concern.

▯ Subjective severity of complaints was measured with a 5-point Likert scale, with 0 indication the lowest severity and 4 the highest severity.

▯ Expected improvement due to the study medication was measured with a 11-point Likert scale, with 0 indication no improvement and 10 a great amount of improvement.

Supplementary table 3. Treatment success and adequate relief in the per-protocol analyses.

	Peppermint oil (N =44)	Placebo (N = 49)	Peppermint sweets (N = 44)
Treatment success, frequency (%)	20 (45.5) ^a	19 (38.8) ^{a,b}	17 (38.6) ^b
Adequate relief, frequency (%)	25 (56.8) ^c	26 (53.1) ^{c,d}	25 (56.8) ^d

^a OR 1.24 (97.5% CI 0.45 – 3.39); *P*=0.64). ^b OR 0.94 (97.5% CI 0.33 – 2.69); *P*=0.89). ^c OR 1.16 (97.5% CI 0.46 – 2.97); *P*=0.72). ^d OR 1.16 (97.5% CI 0.46 – 2.97); *P*=0.72)

Supplementary table 4. Logistic regression analysis to identify factors predicting treatment success at T2.

Predictor*	Simple logistic regression		Multiple logistic regression	
	OR (97.5% CI)	P-value	OR (97.5% CI)	P-value
Sex (male vs female)	0.91 (0.46 – 1.79)	.74		
Age at inclusion (years)	0.93 (0.83 – 1.04)	.13	0.85 (0.71 – 1.01)	.04
First-line family member with FAPD	0.72 (0.33 -1.54)	.33	0.47 (0.12 – 1.91)	.23
Diagnosis (IBS vs. FAP-NOS)	0.99 (0.51 – 1.89)	.96		
IBS subtype (IBS-M as reference)				
IBS-C	0.45 (0.13 – 1.56)	.15	0.67 (0.15 – 3.10)	.56
IBS-D	0.37 (0.08 – 1.73)	.15	0.58 (0.10 – 3.45)	.50
IBS-U	0.49 (0.10 – 2.48)	.32	0.84 (0.13 – 5.63)	.84
Duration of symptoms (in years)	0.92 (0.83 – 1.02)	.06	0.96 (0.82 – 1.11)	.52
Gastro-enteritis prior to start of complaints	1.84 (0.55 – 6.18)	.26	2.16 (0.34 – 13.87)	.35
Major life events prior to start of complaints	0.65 (0.32 – 1.34)	.18	0.73 (0.22 – 2.49)	.57
Including center (academic vs teaching center)	0.59 (0.27 – 1.29)	.13	0.99 (0.25 – 3.84)	.98
Abdominal pain intensity at baseline	0.94 (0.78 – 1.12)	.41		
Abdominal pain duration at baseline (hours)	0.96 (0.90 – 1.02)	.12	0.96 (0.87 – 1.06)	.31
Abdominal pain frequency at baseline (days)	0.98 (0.78 – 1.23)	.84		
Total quality of life (PedsQL 4.0)	1.00 (0.97 – 1.03)	.78		
Anxiety scores (RCADS-25)	1.02 (0.95 – 1.09)	.57		
Depression scores (RCADS-25)	1.03 (0.94 – 1.14)	.44		
Expected improvement due to study medication	1.02 (0.86 – 1.20)	.84		
Compliance to study treatment	1.00 (0.99 – 1.02)	.77		
Preference for study treatment (no preference as reference)	1.56 (0.47 – 5.20)	.41		

Mild peppermint oil preference	0.61 (0.21 – 1.73)	.28		
Strong peppermint oil preference	1.40 (0.35 – 5.56)	.58		
Mild peppermint sweet preference	1.29 (0.43 – 3.90)	.60		
Strong peppermint oil preference				

**Treatment group
(placebo as reference)**

Peppermint oil	1.34 (0.58 – 3.09)	.44	1.16 (0.27 – 4.96)	.85
Peppermint sweets	1.04 (0.45 – 2.45)	.91	0.90 (0.24 – 3.33)	.81

* For continuous predictors, the OR should be interpreted as the change in OR with one unit increase in the predictor value.

Supplementary table 5. Logistic regression analysis to identify factors predicting adequate relief at T2.

Predictor*	Simple logistic regression		Multiple logistic regression	
	OR (97.5% CI)	P-value	OR (97.5% CI)	P-value
Sex (male vs female)	1.32 (0.70 – 2.50)	.33		
Age at inclusion (years)	0.93 (0.83 – 1.03)	.10	0.98 (0.86 – 1.11)	.71
First-line family member with FAPD	0.89 (0.46 – 1.75)	.71		
Diagnosis (IBS vs. FAP-NOS)	0.85 (0.46 – 1.56)	.54		
IBS subtype (IBS-M as reference)				
IBS-C	0.63 (0.19 – 2.07)	.38		
IBS-D	0.46 (0.11 – 1.89)	.22		
IBS-U	0.68 (0.16 – 2.81)	.54		
Duration of symptoms (in years)	0.95 (0.87 – 1.03)	.15	0.93 (0.84 – 1.04)	.15
Gastro-enteritis prior to start of complaints	1.34 (0.44 – 4.07)	.55		
Major life events prior to start of complaints	0.62 (0.32 – 1.21)	.11	0.87 (0.38 -2.01)	.71
Including center (academic vs teaching center)	0.78 (0.40 – 1.53)	.41		
Abdominal pain intensity at baseline	0.73 (0.61 – 0.88)	<.001	0.63 (0.44 – 0.90)	.003
Abdominal pain duration at baseline (hours)	0.90 (0.84 – 0.97)	<.001	0.94 (0.86 – 1.02)	.09
Abdominal pain frequency at baseline (days)	0.84 (0.67 – 1.05)	.08	1.39 (0.90 – 2.16)	.09
Total quality of life (PedsQL 4.0)	1.03 (1.01 – 1.06)	.01	1.02 (0.98 – 1.06)	.40
Anxiety scores (RCADS-25)	0.96 (0.90 – 1.02)	.11	1.00 (0.92 – 1.10)	.92
Depression scores (RCADS-25)	0.96 (0.88 – 1.04)	.26		
Expected improvement due to study medication	1.18 (1.00 – 1.39)	.02	1.13 (0.94 – 1.35)	.15
Compliance to study treatment	1.01 (0.99 – 1.02)	.40		
Preference for study treatment (no preference as reference)	0.57 (0.18 – 1.84)	.28		

Mild peppermint oil preference	0.96 (0.41 – 2.26)	.92		
Strong peppermint oil preference	1.41 (0.38 – 5.26)	.56		
Mild peppermint sweet preference	1.32 (0.48 – 3.63)	.54		
Strong peppermint oil preference				

**Treatment group
(placebo as
reference)**

Peppermint oil	1.19 (0.56 - 2.57)	.60	1.03 (0.39 – 2.74)	.94
Peppermint sweets	0.81 (0.39 – 1.71)	.53	0.71 (0.28 – 1.81)	.77

*** For continuous predictors, the OR should be interpreted as the change in OR with one unit increase in the predictor value.**

Supplementary table 6. Treatment success and adequate relief at T1, T2, and T3.

	Peppermint oil (N = 75)	Placebo (N = 75)	Peppermint sweets (N = 78)	P-value
Treatment success, frequency (%)				
T1	24 (32.0)	21 (28.0)	23 (29,5)	.65
T2	33 (44.0)	28 (37.3)	30 (38.7)	.59
T3	30 (40.0)	28 (37.3)	35 (44.9)	.59
Adequate relief, frequency (%)				
T1	24 (34.3)	19 (26.0)	16 (20.8)	.18
T2	40 (53.3)	37 (49.3)	35 (44.9)	.54
T3	26 (39.4)	31 (47.0)	28 (37.3)	.48

† By one-way analysis of variance.

Supplementary table 7. Secondary endpoints during treatment and follow-up for all treatment groups.

	Peppermint oil (N = 75)	Placebo (N = 75)	Peppermint sweets (N = 78)	P-value
Abdominal pain intensity score, mean (SD)¶				
T0	4.7 (1.6)	5.2 (2.0)	4.9 (2.0)	
T1	4.1 (2.2)	4.5 (2.1)	4.4 (2.1)	1.0
T2	3.7 (2.2)	4.3 (2.6)	4.1 (2.3)	.64
T3	3.7 (2.0)	4.1 (2.1)	3.8 (2.1)	.66
Abdominal pain duration, hours, median (IQR)				
T0	2.2 (1.1 – 4.6)	2.7 (1.0 – 7.9)	2.3 (1.1 – 5.6)	
T1	2.8 (0.8 – 6.0)	2.7 (1.1 – 7.3)	2.4 (1.1 – 7.0)	.84
T2	1.7 (0.4 – 4.6)	2.1 (0.8 – 6.6)	2.1 (0.7 – 5.8)	.43
T3	2.8 (0.9 – 5.8)	3.8 (1.5 – 8.3)	3.6 (0.8 – 7.8)	.77
Abdominal pain weekly frequency, days, median (IQR)				
T0	6.0 (5.0 – 7.0)	7.0 (6.0 – 7.0)	6.9 (5.0 – 7.0)	
T1	6.0 (4.0 – 7.0)	6.0 (5.0 – 7.0)	6.1 (5.0 – 7.0)	.11
T2	5.0 (3.0 – 7.0)	6.0 (3.0 – 7.0)	6.0 (4.0 – 7.0)	.43
T3	6.0 (3.6 – 7.0)	6.1 (5.0 – 7.0)	6.0 (3.0 – 7.0)	.77
Defecation frequency per day, median (IQR)				
T0	1.3 (1.0 – 1.8)	1.0 (0.7 – 1.6)	1.1 (0.7 – 1.6)	
T1	1.4 (0.9 – 2.0)	1.2 (0.8 – 1.7)	1.0 (0.8 – 1.7)	.69
T2	1.4 (1.0 – 1.9)	1.2 (0.9 – 1.8)	1.1 (0.8 – 1.7)	.63
T3	1.4 (1.0 – 2.0)	1.3 (1.0 – 1.8)	1.2 (0.8 – 1.8)	.93
Stool consistency, mean (SD) †				
T0	3.9 (0.9)	3.8 (0.8)	3.9 (0.9)	
T1	3.9 (0.7)	3.8 (0.6)	4.0 (0.7)	.77
T2	3.9 (0.7)	3.9 (0.6)	4.0 (0.6)	.81
T3	4.0 (0.7)	3.9 (0.6)	4.0 (0.6)	.41
Use of painkillers, days, median (IQR) ††				
T0	0.2 (0.0 – 0.4)	0.2 (0.0 – 0.5)	0.1 (0.0 – 0.4)	
T1	0.3 (0.0 – 0.9)	0.2 (0.0 – 0.6)	0.2 (0.0 – 0.6)	.16
T2	0.3 (0.0 – 0.7)	0.2 (0.0 – 0.6)	0.1 (0.0 – 0.4)	.81
T3	0.3 (0.0 – 0.6)	0.3 (0.0 – 0.6)	0.2 (0.0 – 0.6)	.31
School absence, days, median (IQR) ‡				
T0	0.0 (0.0 – 1.1) N = 66	0.0 (0.0 – 1.0) N = 61	0.0 (0.0 – 2.0) N = 67	
T1	0.0 (0.0 – 2.0) N = 54	0.0 (0.0 – 1.0) N = 55	0.0 (0.0 – 1.0) N = 57	.72
T2	0.0 (0.0 – 1.0) N = 49	0.0 (0.0 – 1.8) N = 48	0.0 (0.0 – 2.0) N = 53	.79
T3	0.0 (0.0 – 1.0) N = 46	0.0 (0.0 – 1.0) N = 37	0.0 (0.0 – 1.0) N = 45	.57

Total quality of life (PedsQL 4.0), mean (SD) \bar{T}				
T0	67.3 (12.7) N = 60	67.0 (12.9) N = 60	67.1 (13.9) N = 65	
T2	74.0 (11.8) N = 56	75.7 (12.3) N = 54	74.0 (12.3) N = 50	.93
Physical quality of life (PedsQL 4.0), mean (SD) \bar{T}				
T0	67.5 (13.5) N = 60	65.9 (16.7) N = 60	67.2 (15.4) N = 65	
T2	76.7 (12.6) N = 56	78.0 (13.9) N = 54	75.5 (13.6) N = 50	.81
Psychosocial quality of life (PedsQL 4.0), mean (SD) \bar{T}				
T0	67.1 (14.0) N = 60	67.5 (13.2) N = 60	67.0 (14.5) N = 65	
T2	72.6 (13.0) N = 56	74.5 (13.5) N = 54	73.1 (12.9) N = 50	.96
Anxiety (RCADS-25), mean (SD) $\bar{\text{¶}}$				
T0	9.3 (5.5) N=59	7.1 (5.3) N = 60	9.1 (5.3) N = 65	
T2	8.3 (5.3) N=54	6.5 (5.2) N=52	7.6 (5.3) N=50	.48
Depression (RCADS-25), mean (SD) $\bar{\text{‡}}$				
T0	6.7 (4.0) N=59	5.6 (3.7) N = 60	7.0 (4.0) N = 65	
T2	6.2 (3.5) N=54	5.3 (4.4) N=52	5.9 (3.6) N=50	.32

$\bar{\text{¶}}$ Abdominal pain intensity was scored on a scale from 0 to 10, with 0 indicating no pain and 10 the worst imaginable pain.

┆ Stool consistency was assessed with the use of the Bristol Stool Form Scale, which ranges from 1 to 7, with 1 indicating hard stool and 7 indicating watery diarrhea

$\bar{\text{δ}}$ Somatization was scored on a scale from 0 to 140, with 0 indication lowest somatization and 140 the highest somatization.

$\bar{\text{#}}$ Use of painkillers was scored as the number of days of that week that the patient took a painkiller.

$\bar{\text{α}}$ School absence was scored as the number of days of the last two weeks that the patient was absent from school.

$\bar{\text{T}}$ Quality of life scores were scored on a scale from 0 to 100, with 0 indicating worst quality of life and 100 the best quality of life.

$\bar{\text{¶}}$ Anxiety was scored on a scale from 0 to 60, with 0 indicating lowest severity of anxiety and 60 the most severe anxiety.

$\bar{\text{‡}}$ Depression was scored on a scale from 0 to 15, with 0 indication lowest severity of depression and 15 the highest severity of depression.

Supplementary table 8. Ease of use, taste and beliefs regarding which treatment was allocated.

	Peppermint oil (N = 75)	Placebo (N = 75)	Peppermint sweets (N = 78)	P-value
I like the taste of the pills, frequency (%)	N = 55	N = 53	N = 50	<.001
– Strongly disagree	12 (21.8)	5 (9.4)	4 (8.0)	
– Disagree	12 (21.8)	14 (26.4)	2 (4.0)	
– Do not agree or disagree	22 (40.0)	24 (45.3)	13 (26.0)	
– Agree	6 (10.9)	8 (15.1)	10 (20.0)	
– Strongly agree	3 (5.5)	2 (3.8)	21 (42.0)	
The pills were ease to use and swallow, frequency (%)				.27
– Strongly disagree	4 (7.3)	5 (11.3)	5 (10.0)	
– Disagree	7 (12.7)	3 (5.7)	4 (8.0)	
– Do not agree or disagree	8 (14.5)	10 (18.9)	5 (10.0)	
– Agree	20 (36.4)	19 (35.8)	11 (22.0)	
– Strongly agree	16 (29.1)	15 (28.3)	25 (50.0)	
Treatment group patients believed to be allocated to, frequency (%)			NA	.18
– Peppermint oil	35 (64.8)	25 (47.2)		
– Placebo	6 (11.1)	10 (18.9)		
– No idea	13 (24.1)	18 (34.0)		
Extra peppermint sweets taken per day, median (IQR)	0.0 (0.0 – 0.0)	0.0 (0.0 – 0.0)	0.0 (0.0 – 1.0)	.006

Supplementary appendices

Appendix S1.

Inclusion criteria:

- Children aged ≥ 8 years and ≤ 18 years
- Diagnosis of IBS or FAP-NOS according to the Rome IV criteria. ¹
- An average daily pain rate of ≥ 3 of 10 on the Wong Baker Faces Pain Scale (This is a validated pain scale to measure pain intensity). ²⁴

Rome IV criteria for irritable bowel syndrome (IBS) in children and adolescents:

Diagnostic criteria* must include **all** of the following:

- Abdominal pain at least 4 days per month associated with one or more of the following:
 - a) Related to defecation
 - b) A change in frequency of stool
 - c) A change in form (appearance) of stool
- In children with constipation, the pain does not resolve with resolution of the constipation (children in whom the pain resolves have functional constipation, not irritable bowel syndrome)
- After appropriate evaluation, the symptoms cannot be fully explained by another medical condition

* *Criteria fulfilled for at least 2 months before diagnosis*

Rome IV criteria for functional abdominal pain – not otherwise specified (FAP-NOS) in children and adolescents:

Diagnostic criteria* must be fulfilled 4 times per month and include **all** of the following:

- Episodic or continuous abdominal pain that does not occur solely during physiologic events (e.g., eating, menses)
- Insufficient criteria for irritable bowel syndrome, functional dyspepsia, or abdominal migraine
- After appropriate evaluation, the abdominal pain cannot be fully explained by another medical condition.

* *Criteria fulfilled at least 2 months before diagnosis.*

Exclusion criteria:

- Current treatment by another health care professional for abdominal symptoms
- Previous use of peppermint oil for these abdominal complaints
- Known hypersensitivity to mints or peppermint oil
- Gastrointestinal blood loss
- Recurrent or unexplained fevers
- Decreased growth velocity
- History of previous abdominal surgeries in the past 3 months
- Significant chronic health condition requiring specialty care (e.g., lithiasis, ureteropelvic junction obstruction, sickle cell, cerebral palsy, hepatic, hematopoietic, renal, endocrine, or metabolic diseases) that could potentially impact the child's ability to participate or confound the results of the study
- Known concomitant organic gastrointestinal disease

- Current use of drugs which influence gastrointestinal motility, such as erythromycin, azithromycin, butyl scopolamine, domperidone, mebeverine and Iberogast. If laxatives are being used (in patients with IBS-C) they can continue using them during the study.
- Current use of proton-pump inhibitors
- Insufficient knowledge of the Dutch language

Pregnancy or current lactation. Women with childbearing potential must have a negative urine pregnancy test within 7 days prior to first dose of study treatment.